

ESPOUSAL (ADOPTION) OF DIGITAL BANKING AMONG WORKING WOMEN IN URBAN AREAS OF PALGHAR DISTRICT DURING COVID-19 OUTBREAK

Sonal Sandesh Raul*

ABSTRACT

Internet banking has transformed the traditional way of banking and has brought new dimensions to the banking sector. This research describes the current state of digital banking in the outbreak of COVID-19. The study focuses on Espousal (adoption) of digital banking in COVID-19 crisis. A primary survey was conducted using a structured questionnaire for working women in urban areas of Palghar District, which focuses on woman's perspective for using as well as not using digital banking services. Digital banking is highly accepted among working women in urban areas of Palghar District. The working women on boarding digitally in the time of COVID-19 crises have found to be increased. Majority of women have not visited bank branches in personal during the COVID-19 outbreak they prefer digital banking over traditional banking. This study also focuses on the problems faced by working women in urban areas of Palghar District while using digital banking.

Keywords- Digital banking, online banking, UPI, mobile banking

INTRODUCTION

The only safe place for humans is confined to their individual homes, as the worldwide outbreak of COVID-19 creates havoc in the public life of people. Every day the number of affected cases shows a sharp rise. The situation can be brought to control only with the right precaution and practice of social distancing. During the lockdown situation, only the essential services have been kept open and banking comes under it as well. Banking operations such as cash deposits, withdrawals, clearing of cheques and other traditional teller services had to be executed by maintaining a safe distance of at least a meter.

The National Payments Corporation of India (NPCI) has recently declared that the payment systems in India were up and running during the coronavirus lockdown. Digital payment platforms are making life easier for people, as the payment modes like UPI are easy to adopt, along with being secure. Customers are able to purchase items, transfer money by registering to the apps after getting their mobile numbers verified.

However, physical access to any place and even banks is increasingly becoming potentially risky and hazardous. To cope with the situation, digital banking and digital payment systems come to the aid of people for the

*Assistant Professor, SAS Institute of Management Studies, Mumbai

necessary convenience they require during this time. It not only provides help with the banking services during the lockdown, but it also helps people maintain the social distancing protocol during the pandemic. Since the spread of the virus is from person to person, currency notes could be potential carriers. Digitalization in the banking sector opens up a whole world full of possibilities both for the institutions themselves and for consumers in the outbreak of COVID-19.

Today, due to COVID-19 outbreak Digital Banking redefined the style of banking, the trend towards digitalization is increasing. Customers manage their banking transactions from their home without the involvement of banking staff.

By the end of last century, banks began offering 24 hours services to customers by using technology, but now customer can carry 24 hours banking facility with them, because of there smart phones. Digital banking has offered many comfortable features and possibilities to people like:

1. Online Banking

The online banking provides banking anytime and anywhere. Throughout the year, website services mentioned below are offered:

- A detailed View of summary of customers account and transaction.
- You can view and print account statements and check balances
- Deposits which saves a lot of time and money for you.
- services allowing to export your account histories to third-party accounting software
- Set up online payments and Transfer funds from one account to another

2. Personal Finance Planning

Because of fintech, Banks have come up with advanced websites which have different banking options like, tools that help to analyze investments, loan calculators, tax preparation , financial planning tools, , premium calculators, etc. As a result, most of the financial planning which needs bank staff can now be done efficiently without the need to personally visit a bank.

3. Mobile banking options

Mobile banking is a service provided by a bank which allows its customers to conduct financial transactions using a mobile device. Banks build mobile friendly websites and have features that help customers to efficiently use banking services with the help mobile. Within few clicks on the mobile customers can transfer the money and pay his/her dues.

4. Unified Payment System (UPI)

UPI was developed by NPCI which helps in inter-bank transactions. It is instant payment system. Money can be sent or requested with the help of Virtual Payment Address (VPA), Mobile number (Send or request money from/to bank account mapped using mobile number), Account number & IFSC, Aadhaar (Send money to bank account mapped using Aadhaar number) and QR code (Send money by QR code which has enclosed VPA, Account number and IFSC or Mobile number) Reserve Bank of India regulates this interface and works by instantly transferring funds among two bank accounts from mobile platform.

5. Digital Wallet

Now a day's mobile wallets (m-wallets), E- wallets or virtual wallets have become quite popular. With these (Paytm, G-pay, BHIM,

PhonePe) mobile wallets, you can pay just by using your smartphone. After demonetization, more people have started using m-wallets.

6. Rewards and Loyalty Program(s)

These digitally integrated programs has help customer acquisition and retention by introducing cost-effective and measurable reward distribution technique, it is also a business innovation technique which results in growth by creating more profitable and loyal customers to the bank. Customers can later redeem the points earned by them for various products, travel experiences, etc.

7. Non-Internet Based Phone Banking

These services include SMS, Missed Call and USSD banking. With SMS and missed call banking services you are only required to send a text or give a missed call on some specific numbers. These services can be accessed from anywhere and at any time since they do not need an internet connection. They are free services and all transactions are completely cashless.

8. Digital Coupons and cash back

A coupon is a ticket a small card or a document which is used for discount or rebate while purchasing a product. Indian banks give discounts on numerous items through coupons and cash back facility.

9. Automatic Bill Payments

Banks allow customers to link their bills to their account and get it paid by a particular time automatically with customers consent.

9. Secure Message Alerts

Digital banking provides instant real-time notifications. For example, you can be notified when transactions are completed or denied, a bill

payment date is approaching, your bank balance has reached a specified target amount, details of your account were changed, there were failed attempts to log into your account.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research paper is aimed at examining the Espousal (adoption) of digital banking among working women in urban areas of Palghar District during covid-19 outbreak and to ascertain the factors encouraging and discouraging the usage of digital banking, Problems faced while using digital banking etc. This Study is based on primary data accumulated by circulating Google-form, which was filled by 133 respondents during the month of May 2020 out of which 102 were taken under consideration for research, rest of the responses were eliminated as they were incomplete. The sampling procedure adopted for the present study is treated as stratified random sampling method.

OBJECTIVES

- To study the factors responsible for Espousal of digital banking among working women in urban areas of Palghar District during COVID-19
- To study the frequency of working women using Digital Banking Services before COVID-19 outbreak and during COVID-19 outbreak.
- To study the factors that restricts usage of digital banking among working women in urban areas of Palghar District during COVID-19 outbreak.
- To study the problems faced by the working women while using digital banking in urban areas of Palghar District during covid-19 outbreak

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION-**Users of Digital Banking**

Usage of Digital Banking	Users	Percentage of users	Non-Users	Percentage of non-users	Total Responses
Before COVID-19	76	74.5%	26	25.49%	102
During COVID-19	89	87.25	13	12.74%	102

The above table states that 25.49% of respondents are Non users of Digital Banking Services and 74.5% of respondents are using Digital Banking services before the outbreak of COVID-19. During the outbreak of COVID-19 the total of non-users declined to 12.74% from 25.49% and the users of digital banking increased to 87.25% from 74.5%.

Non-Users Perspectives for not using digital banking during COVID-19

Factors which restricts the usage Digital Banking	No.of Respondents	Percentage
Prefer visiting Bank in personal	0	0
Security & Privacy	7	53.84
Technological Barrier	4	30.76
Not user friendly	1	7.69
Lack of trust	1	7.69
Total	13	100

From the above table we could say that 53.84% of working women who don't use digital banking are concern with security and privacy issues while on-boarding digitally, 30.76% don't use digital banking because they face technological barriers and 7.69% of working women restricts themselves from using digital banking as it is not user friendly for them also they don't trust digital banking.

Users Perspective**Factors influencing Digital Banking during COVID-19**

Usage Reasons	No.of Respondents	Percentage
Cash back/ Discounts	0	0
Ease to operate	19	21.34
Lack of mobility due to lock down	6	6.74
To avoid personal contact in covid-19	22	24.71
Saves time	29	32.58
To avoid virus transmission	8	8.98
Numerous modes to use Digital banking	5	5.61
Total	89	100

The above table shows the major reasons for respondents to use digital banking during the outbreak of covid19 is “saves times” with 32.58% respondents, “To avoid personal contact in covid-19” with 24.71% respondents, “Ease to operate” with 21.34% followed by 8.98% of respondents saying “To avoid virus transmission”.

Frequency of using Digital Banking services

Usage by Respondents	Before COVID-19		During COVID-19	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Once in a month	11	12.35	7	7.86
Once in 2 weeks	29	32.58	11	12.35
Once a week	23	25.84	28	31.46
2-3 times in a week	18	20.22	27	30.33
Daily	8	8.89	16	17.97
Total	89	100	89	100

Before outbreak of Covid-19 Digital Banking was used by 32.58% of respondents once in two weeks, 25.84% of respondents were using digital banking once a week, 20.22% were using digital banking 2-3 times a week followed by 12.35% using digital banking once in a month and only 8.89% of respondents were using digital banking on daily basis. Whereas, with the outbreak of Covid-19 the use of digital banking services has increased. 31.46% of respondents used digital banking once a week, 30.33% respondents used digital banking 2-3 times in a week. The major increase was observed in the usage of digital banking in daily basis from 8.89% to 17.97%. Working women using digital banking services once a month was also decreased to 7.86%.

Problems faced while using digital banking

Major problems faced	Frequency	Percentage
Transaction Failure	26	29.21
Long processing time	14	15.73
Delay in payments & transaction	11	12.35
Unrevised Funds	3	3.37
Frauds and scams	10	11.23
Lack of authenticity	8	8.98
Connectivity issue	17	19.10
Total	89	100

Above table shows the major problems faced by the working women in urban areas of Palghar District, Where 29.21% of respondents have faced transaction failure, 19.10% of respondents have face connectivity issues, 15.73% respondents have concern with long processing time followed by delay in payments and transactions, frauds and scams, lack of authenticity and unrevised funds respectively.

Mode used for Digital Banking

Respondents were also asked about the mode which they prefer and use for digital payments and services offered by banks. Mobile banking, UPI and Internet banking were mentioned by the respondents.

Frequency of visiting a bank in personal

On asking the respondents about their frequency of visiting a bank in personal before COVID-19 outbreak and during COVID-19 outbreak it was observed that 77.2% of respondents have not visited bank in the month of March, April and till mid of May. Respondents visiting bank once in two months decreased to 2.9% from 16.9%, the frequency of visiting bank once in month decreased to 12.5% from 19.5%. The percentage of respondents visiting a branch twice in month also decreased to 6.6% from 11%.

FINDINGS

- In the present study it is found that Espousal (adoption) rate of digital banking among working women in urban areas of Palghar District is already high, but due to COVID-19 additional 12.75% of working women have started using digital banking services.
- Non users of digital banking services restrict their usage as they feel there is lack of security, there is no privacy in using digital banking services, the financial technology used is complicated and difficult to use.
- The major factor which influence working women's in urban areas of Palghar District to use and adopt digital banking services in COVID-19 outbreak is "Time". Digital banking saves lot of time and helps with real time guidance and support. Other than time women also wanted to avoid personal contact as well as virus transmission in the

time of covid-19 outbreak, so they preferred digital banking services.

- The frequency in which women use digital banking was also increased. Before outbreak of covid-19 only 8.89% working women were using digital banking daily but due to covid-19 now 17.97% women use digital banking on daily basis. COVID-19 has increased the frequency of people using digital banking.
- 3 major problems faced by the woman that use digital banking are frequent transaction failures; difficulty in getting connected digitally, connectivity errors and also delays in payments and transactions.
- Majority of the working women use Mobile banking, UPI and Internet banking as a platform for availing digital banking services.
- Women in urban areas of Palghar District has limited their visits to bank. The frequency of visiting bank branches in personal has considerably reduced. 77.2% of working women of urban Palghar district has not visited banks in the month of March, April and May.

CONCLUSION

From this study we could find that Digital banking has become a necessary survival weapon and is fundamentally changing the banking industry worldwide. COVID-19 pandemic has brought drastic changes in everyone's lives, and by every measure to prevent it we are going through a great crisis. It is natural to assume that the pandemic will be a turning point in modern history. Banking, too, can become a frictionless experience in coming years.

As a result of the COVID-19 crisis, we are seeing a rise in espousal (adoption) of digital banking services among working women in urban areas of Palghar District and a decline in visits to physical bank branches. The current pandemic has forced women in urban areas of Palghar District, who once resisted online banking to adopt digital banking apps as their new default. The more this population of Palghar District realizes how convenient it is to bank digitally, the less likely they are to go back to physical bank branches. When the COVID-19 situation is past for all of us, it is expected that the Indian Banks will shift its gears to move away from traditional forms of banking to digital banking. The traditional banks will stand the opportunity to leapfrog adopting cutting edge banking technologies and blaze the digital transformation trail.

REFERENCES

- Bilal Ahmad Sheikh & Dr.P.Rajmohan (2017): Adoption of digital banking in India, Asia Pacific Journal of Research, Vol: I. Issue LII, ISSN (Print): 2320-5504.
- Dr. lekshri B(2018): E-Banking in India-Problems & Prospectus,VOL-5,Issur-I, ISSN(PRINT):2393-8774,(ONLINE)2344-0677.
- K Koti: Customer awareness and adaptability towards internet banking: A study of Indian banking industry.Www.socialresearchjournals.com, volume 2, issue 8, p. 63 – 67, Posted: 2016-08.

